

D2.5 - ANALYSIS AND DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABILITY THRESHOLDS

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides a comprehensive assessment of sustainability thresholds for 21 indicators identified within the SUSTRACK framework as relevant to monitoring the EU's transition toward a circular bioeconomy. It analyses how these indicators relate to the planetary boundaries (PBs) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), thereby linking the measurement of bioeconomy performance to both ecological limits and social objectives.

The analysis demonstrates that while a wide range of indicators is available to track bioeconomic activities, only a few are explicitly designed to reflect ecological thresholds or early warning functions. Defining scientifically robust, absolute thresholds for many of these indicators remains beyond current feasibility, given the complexity of the Earth system and the evolving state of scientific knowledge. Fixed threshold values are also often neither meaningful nor conducive to informed decision-making, as they obscure systemic interdependencies, regional variations, and shifting pressures on planetary systems.

Consequently, the report adopts policy-based performance thresholds, drawing from existing EU legislative and strategic frameworks, such as the Effort Sharing Regulation, the LULUCF Regulation, the Waste Framework Directive, and the Energy Efficiency Directive, where available. These serve as actionable and credible proxies for sustainability monitoring. By anchoring indicator assessment in established policy targets, the report ensures consistency with EU governance structures while maintaining alignment with the overarching ambition of remaining within planetary boundaries.

Each of the 21 indicators was examined in relation to the planetary boundaries it directly or indirectly influences and the SDGs it supports. The planetary boundaries framework provided the conceptual foundation for this analysis. Current scientific evidence indicates that seven of the nine boundaries have already been transgressed, while only stratospheric ozone depletion and atmospheric aerosol loading remain within the safe operating space. The indicators examined in this report are most strongly associated with these already exceeded boundaries, underscoring the need for targeted monitoring and ambitious performance thresholds in these domains.

Overall, the report establishes a structured basis for monitoring the sustainability performance of the EU circular bioeconomy through policy-aligned thresholds, providing an analytical bridge between statistical indicators and sustainability frameworks.

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List of abbreviations	
Abbreviation/ Acronym	Description
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
CBBE	Circular bio-based economy
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
UN	United Nations
EU-BMS	EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Traceable
GVA	Gross Value Added
GHG	Greenhouse gas
PRTR	Pollutant Release and Transfer Register
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
LULUCF	Land use, land use-change and forestry
NACE	Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne
CMUR	Circular material use rate
DMC	Domestic material consumption
BIC	Bio-based Industry Consortium
WFD	Waste Framework Directive
Mtoe	Mega Tonnes of Oil Equivalent
ETS	Emissions Trading System
ESR	Effort Sharing Regulation
AFOLU	Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
PFCs	Perfluorocarbons
F&B	Food and beverage
EEA	European Environment Agency
WEI	Water exploitation index

1. INTRODUCTION

The assessment and tracking of sustainability performance have become increasingly significant for policymakers, as human production and consumption continue to place growing pressure on natural resources and ecosystems. Most of these systems can only absorb disruption up to a certain limit, or “tipping point”, beyond which abrupt ecological changes with severe social, economic, and environmental consequences, often irreversible, are likely to occur. To prevent such outcomes, it is essential to determine and monitor these limits. Crucially, scientific research on sustainability performance should be translated into practical early warning systems that enable policymakers to recognise risks and respond timely and effectively.

Although a wide range of environmental indicators for assessing sustainability has been developed and is currently in use, only a limited subset is designed to capture threshold dynamics. The majority of existing indicator frameworks lack clearly defined target values and fail to provide early warnings about critical “danger zones” that signal when ecological thresholds are close to being exceeded or when conditions of environmental sustainability have been secured (Srebotnjak et al., 2010). This gap undermines the ability of existing monitoring systems to support evidence-based policymaking.

Hammond et al. (1995) define an indicator as “something that provides a clue to a matter of larger significance or makes perceptible a trend of phenomenon that is not immediately detectable. [...] Thus, an indicator’s significance extends beyond what is actually measured to a larger phenomenon of interest.” By identifying key statistics of complex phenomena in a digestible form, indicators support understanding, analysis, and ultimately decision-making. Especially for environmental indicators, however, merely monitoring the indicators is not sufficient for informed policymaking; thresholds are required to establish an appropriate framework for climate protection policies. Since discussions about climate targets are often accompanied by questions on their implications on economic growth and socioeconomic circumstances, thresholds are specifically important for debates on the limits to growth and beyond gross domestic product (GDP) policy development. In its communication on GDP and beyond, the European Commission emphasised the importance of respecting the limits of the planet’s natural resources, stating that: “*scientists are seeking to identify related physical environmental threshold values and highlight the potential long-term or irreversible consequences of crossing them. For policymaking it is important to know the ‘danger zones’ before the actual tipping points are reached, thereby identifying alert levels.*” (EC, 2009).

To operationalise sustainability goals, such as climate neutrality, each indicator should be associated with a reference point against which performance can be assessed. In the literature, this is often referred to as a “performance threshold”. Ladu and Morone (2021) define a performance threshold as “*the point at which an indicator can be considered to have performed as expected*”. These thresholds may be defined relative to an ideal condition (e.g. zero emissions), a policy target (e.g. circular economy benchmarks), a reference scenario (e.g. life cycle assessment limits), or a minimum requirement (e.g. social sustainability).

However, it is crucial to distinguish performance thresholds from sustainability thresholds. Sustainability thresholds reflect biophysical limits of the Earth system and crossing them signals that environmental stability and resilience are at risk. Performance thresholds, by contrast, express the level of progress that society or policymakers expect to achieve. While approaching a sustainability threshold implies danger, meeting a performance threshold indicates success. For performance thresholds to be meaningful in the context of climate and environmental protection, they must be aligned with and remain within sustainability thresholds. This alignment ensures that

policy ambition does not merely track incremental progress, but actively contributes to keeping human activities within the Earth’s safe operating space.

In this context, the planetary boundaries framework introduced in 2009 offers a scientifically grounded approach to defining global environmental thresholds. It presents a paradigm shift in our understanding of the Earth’s biophysical limits and the safe operating space within which human activities can carry on without irreversibly damaging the Earth system to a point where it is no longer stable or functional. The framework originally assessed only seven planetary boundaries but now includes nine, namely climate change, biosphere integrity, land-system change, freshwater use, nutrient pollution (biogeochemical flows), ocean acidification, atmospheric aerosol loading, stratospheric ozone depletion, and finally the introduction of novel entities. The 2023 update which expanded the number of planetary boundaries, also assessed that six of the nine boundaries are already transgressed. By 2025, seven of the planetary boundaries were crossed (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Planetary boundaries update 2025
(Source: Azote for Stockholm Resilience Centre, based on analysis in Sakschewski and Caesar et al. 2025; licensed under CC BY-NC-ND 3.0)

While the planetary boundaries framework is meanwhile well-established and commonly used or referenced in scientific research, it sparked huge debate, inter alia, around how to downscale such a global concept to a regional level and extract meaningful information for country-level decision-making (Ferretto et al., 2022). Furthermore, only relying on the framework for the identification of thresholds for environmental indicators and the development of climate policies neglects socioeconomic goals. A notable attempt at addressing this issue is the “doughnut” concept developed by Kate Raworth. The doughnut is made up of two concentric rings. The inner

ring represents the social foundation and guarantees that everyone's essential needs are met, while the outer ring represents the ecological ceiling, which ensures that humans do not overshoot Earth's planetary boundaries. The doughnut-shaped zone between both rings constitutes a safe and just space where people can thrive without irreversibly harming the planet.

In this context, the SUSTRACK project contributes to determining sustainability thresholds within the context of a circular and bio-based economy (CBBE). Specifically, the objective of this report is to describe and explore how the 21 indicators included in the SUSTRACK Dashboard relate to both the planetary boundaries and the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the UN, drawing conclusions regarding the thresholds identified for each indicator. Additionally, the report aims to identify the indicators for which thresholds are already established through scientific research and translated into (EU) policy targets, as well as those for which no thresholds exist. In doing so, the report helps map existing knowledge, but also highlights how conceptual frameworks can inform the operationalisation of sustainability thresholds for indicators that currently have none set.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Identification of indicators

To build a robust and policy-relevant monitoring system, SUSTRACK developed a systematic methodology for identifying and prioritising indicators of the circular bioeconomy transition that are analytically sound, comparable across countries, and aligned with EU policy priorities. The 7-step methodology is detailed in D2.4 and summarised below.

- **Step 1 - Identification of existing indicators:**
The process started with a comprehensive review of the Joint Research Centre's EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (EU-BMS), currently the most comprehensive initiative tracking bioeconomy progress in Europe. This was complemented with additional sources such as Eurostat, FAO, and project partners' expertise. In total, 242 candidate indicators were identified.
- **Step 2 - SMART screening:**
Indicators were reviewed against SMART criteria (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Traceable). The first filter removed indicators lacking sufficient data coverage ($\geq 50\%$ of 2016-2022 period), poor territorial representativeness, or low reliability. A second filter excluded indicators outside SUSTRACK's scope (e.g. food security, unmanaged environmental stocks, non-EU datasets). This reduced the set to 143 indicators.
- **Step 3 - Relevance and interpretability:**
Remaining indicators were further screened for directional clarity (ability to signal progress or decline unambiguously) and comparability (availability of denominators or normalisation methods). Ambiguous or non-comparable indicators, such as farming intensification or absolute volumes of roundwood removals, were excluded. This refinement produced 112 indicators.
- **Step 4 - Complementing gaps:**
To fill gaps identified in the EU-BMS, additional indicators were introduced, including Resource Productivity (from Eurostat) and GHG emission intensities in bio-based sectors (weighted by bio-based GVA shares). Indicators with insufficient time series or unclear

attribution to the bioeconomy (e.g. PRTR pollutant data, monetisation of externalities) were excluded. This expanded the set to 134 indicators.

- **Step 5 - Normalisation and consolidation:**

All indicators were converted to relative terms (per capita, per unit of output, percentage shares) to allow benchmarking across countries. Redundant metrics were removed (e.g. turnover replaced by GVA, absolute values replaced by productivity measures). LULUCF data were transformed into a distance-to-target score, benchmarked against 2030 national commitments, ensuring fair comparability. After this consolidation, 39 indicators remained. Of the 39 remaining indicators, two relate to the bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs area. For this deliverable, however, no sectoral disaggregation into 10 sectors is applied. Instead, the analysis focuses on the bioeconomy as a whole. Consequently, only two aggregates from the competitiveness domain are considered, instead of 20 individual indicators. In total, this deliverable refers to 21 indicators.

- **Steps 6 and 7 - Organisation:**

Indicators were standardised into a 1-6 scoring scale, adjusted for positive or negative directionality, to allow cross-country comparison. The final indicators were then organised into three policy-relevant areas:

1. Sustainable and renewable resource use (resource efficiency, circularity, biomass contribution),
2. Environmental performance of the bioeconomy (emissions, material and carbon footprints, water use), and
3. Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs (employment, productivity, innovation).

This careful narrowing ensured that the Sustrack Monitoring System remains both comprehensive and operational, providing policymakers and stakeholders with a practical tool to track progress, identify hotspots, and guide a just and sustainable bioeconomy transition towards a circular bioeconomy.

2.2. Identification of thresholds

The aim of this report is to identify the sustainability thresholds of the 21 indicators, as expressed through existing policy targets, and advance the understanding of the broader significance of the processes and variables measured by the indicators by analysing their impacts on and relationships with the planetary boundaries and the SDGs. In doing so, D2.5 underscores the importance of remaining within policy-set thresholds to ensure environmental sustainability and deepens the comprehensive understanding of the indicators' environmental and systemic impacts, thereby strengthening the knowledge foundation needed to guide future policy development.

To achieve this aim, D2.5 adopts a mixed-methods approach combining a policy review, a comprehensive literature review, and an evidence-based consultation with consortium partners.

First, an analysis of EU policy documents was undertaken to determine whether existing policy targets or benchmarks could serve as operational thresholds for the Sustrack indicators. Each indicator was cross-referenced with the relevant policy framework to identify whether an explicit or implicit threshold is already established at the EU level and which policy areas do not or only insufficiently define thresholds.

Then, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to examine the environmental and socio-economic implications of each of the 21 indicators. Both academic and grey literature were considered for that step. The search primarily focused on identifying:

- established relationships between each indicator and the planetary boundaries, and
- environmental impacts associated with the process or variable measured by the indicator, in order to infer potential linkages with the planetary boundaries when these were not explicitly established in the literature.

For the majority of the indicators, explicit relationships to the planetary boundaries are not currently established in the literature. To address this gap, a consultation with consortium partners was conducted to review and discuss the findings of the literature analysis. Through this collaborative process, the report identifies and characterises the indicators' relationships with the planetary boundaries, distinguishing between direct and indirect impacts.

Furthermore, to strengthen the interpretative capacity of the SUSTRACK monitoring system, a methodology was developed to map the potential relationships between bioeconomy indicators and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This exercise does not measure impacts directly, but rather identifies whether indicators, depending on their formulation and the direction of their values, are generally associated with supporting or undermining progress towards specific SDGs.

The starting point was a pool of **566 bioeconomy-related indicators**, systematically organised in an Excel database with their respective units of measurement. This allowed for thematic grouping (environmental, social, bioeconomic, nutritional, cross-cutting) and created a basis for consistent analysis. The methodology involved two complementary steps:

1. **Evidence-based mapping** - A literature review of academic and institutional sources was used to identify explicit references linking indicators to SDGs. These were coded as *strongly positive* (3), *strongly negative* (-3), or *ambivalent* (7) when both directions were documented.
2. **Expert judgment** - For indicators lacking explicit documentation, qualitative reasoning supported by related literature was applied. These cases were coded as *assumed positive* (1), *assumed negative* (-1), or *ambivalent* (7).

A key outcome of the exercise is the recognition that indicators often display **diverging contributions depending on the perspective or SDG lens applied**. In other words, while the same indicator can appear beneficial when aligned with certain SDGs, it may simultaneously conflict with others. For example:

- **Crop protection expenditure** can support SDG 2 (*Zero Hunger*) and SDG 8 (*Decent Work and Economic Growth*) by improving yields and farmers' income under sustainable use. However, when viewed from the perspective of SDG 3 (*Health and Well-being*) or SDG 15 (*Life on Land*), the same indicator highlights risks to human health and biodiversity.

By systematically documenting these relationships, the methodology makes visible the **potential synergies and trade-offs** embedded in bioeconomy trends. It also highlights where context-sensitive interpretation is essential, ensuring that indicators are not considered in isolation but assessed in relation to how they interact with different sustainability goals.

3. RESULTS

3.1. List of selected indicators

The final list of indicators prioritised in the SUSTRACK project for the monitoring of a CBBE is presented below. The list includes 21 indicators and divides them into three key areas (see Table 1).

Table 1: Final list of indicators

Sustainable and renewable resource use	
1	Circular material rate (percentage)
2	Recycling rate of municipal waste (percentage)
3	Total generated biowaste (kilo tonnes dry)
4	Total recovered biowaste (kilo tonnes dry)
5	Energy productivity (euro/kg. oil-eq.)
6	Total food waste generation along supply chain (t/person)
7	Resource productivity (euro/kilogram)
8	Biomass share in domestic material consumption (percentage)
9	Gross final energy consumption renewable share (percentage)
Environmental performance of the bio-based economy	
10	GHG emission intensities by agriculture (NACE A01) (grams per euro)
11	GHG emission intensities by forestry and logging (NACE A02) (grams per euro)
12	GHG emission intensities by fishing and aquaculture (NACE A03) (grams per euro)
13	GHG emission intensities by food, beverage, and tobacco industries (NACE C10-C12) (grams per euro)
14	GHG emission intensities from textiles (NACE C13-C15) (grams per euro)
15	GHG emission intensities from wood products, except furniture (NACE C16) (grams per euro)
16	GHG emission intensities from paper and paper products (NACE C17) (grams per euro)
17	Net GHG emissions from land use, land use change, and forestry (LULUCF) (index)
18	Biomass footprint intensity - Raw material consumption (raw-material kilogram/Euro)
19	Water exploitation index (percentage)
Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs	
20	Bioeconomy gross value added (GVA) per person (1000 euro/person)
21	Share of employment in bio-based sectors (percentage)

3.2. Indicators, Thresholds and Targets

3.2.1. Sustainable and renewable resource use area

Indicator 1: Circular material rate

The circular material use rate (CMUR), commonly referred to as the circularity rate, expresses in percentage terms the proportion of materials that are recycled and reintegrated into the economy, thereby reducing the need for primary raw material extraction within total material consumption. Formally, the circularity rate is calculated as the ratio of the circular use of materials (U) to total material use (M).

Total material use is defined as the sum of domestic material consumption (DMC) and the circular use of materials, such that $M = DMC + U$. The DMC is measured according to economy-wide material flow accounts.

The circular use of materials is estimated based on the quantity of waste processed in domestic recovery facilities (RCV_R), adjusted by subtracting imported waste destined for recycling (IMP_W) and adding exported waste destined for recycling abroad (EXP_W). Data from European statistics on international trade in goods (ITGS) serve to approximate both the volume of imported waste for recycling (IMP_W) and exported waste for recycling (EXP_W).

The circularity rate is formalised as:

Equation 1. Circularity rate

$$CMU = \frac{U}{M} = \frac{(RCV_R - IMP_W + EXP_W)}{DMC + (RCV_R - IMP_W + EXP_W)}$$

A higher circularity rate reflects a greater substitution of secondary raw materials for primary ones, thereby contributing to the reduction of environmental pressures associated with primary resource extraction.

In the EU, the CMUR is a key indicator for monitoring progress toward a circular economy. The EU average CMUR is around 12-13%, meaning only about one-eighth of materials used are recycled. The EU aims to almost double this rate to 22,4% by 2030 as part of its Circular Economy Action Plan and Green Deal targets.

Policy-related performance threshold:

- Doubling of the EU's CMUR from 11.2% in 2020 to 22.4 % by 2023 (EU Circular Economy Action Plan).
- A slightly more ambitious figure of 24% has been proposed under the draft Circular Economy Act, currently under consultation.

This proposed threshold provides a concrete benchmark for evaluating progress in circularity.

The CMUR exerts a predominantly positive direct influence on nearly all planetary boundaries, with the exception of stratospheric ozone depletion, on which it has both indirect positive and negative effects.

Direct positive impacts:

- **Climate Change:** A high circular material rate reduces the need for primary raw material extraction and processing, which are responsible for over 55% of global greenhouse gas emissions. By substituting secondary materials for virgin ones, the energy-intensive processes of mining, refining, and manufacturing are reduced, directly mitigating climate change (by lowering GHG emissions).
- **Ocean Acidification:** The positive impact on this boundary is a second-order consequence of the reduction in fossil fuel consumption linked to primary material processing. As the burning of fossil fuels is the primary driver of atmospheric CO₂ accumulation, which in turn leads to ocean acidification, reducing energy demand through circularity helps to mitigate this process.

- **Biogeochemical Flows:** The extraction and processing of materials are linked to the release of nutrient pollutants into the environment. By reducing the demand for primary materials, a higher circular material rate can help to alleviate the pressure on the nitrogen and phosphorus cycles.
- **Freshwater Change:** Material extraction and processing are highly water-intensive activities. A higher circularity rate directly reduces this demand for blue water, thereby positively impacting the freshwater boundary.
- **Land-system Change:** Resource extraction, especially from mining and agriculture, drives land-use change, including deforestation and habitat loss. A higher circular material rate, by reducing the demand for new material extraction, directly lowers the pressure on land systems.
- **Biosphere Integrity:** A significant portion of biodiversity loss is directly linked to land-use change and habitat destruction driven by material extraction and processing. By reducing the need for virgin resources, a higher circularity rate helps to protect ecosystems and mitigate biodiversity loss.
- **Novel Entities:** The circular economy's focus on retaining materials and products in circulation helps to prevent the dispersion of novel entities, such as plastics and other synthetic chemicals, into the environment. By designing out waste and pollution, this approach directly addresses the root cause of this boundary's transgression.
- **Atmospheric Aerosol Loading:** The processes of mining, industrial manufacturing, and the burning of fossil fuels for energy produce a significant amount of particulate matter and other aerosol pollutants. A higher circular material rate reduces the scale of these activities, thereby mitigating atmospheric aerosol loading.

Indirect positive or neutral impacts:

- **Stratospheric Ozone Depletion:** GHG emissions warm the lower atmosphere (troposphere) while simultaneously cooling the upper atmosphere (stratosphere). This cooling creates conditions that enhance chemical ozone depletion, particularly by forming polar stratospheric clouds (PSCs), which allow ozone-destroying reactions to occur more efficiently. This creates a complex feedback loop where stratospheric cooling, caused by GHGs, can worsen ozone loss, thus negatively impacting the recovery rate of the ozone layer. Increasing the CMUR in a way that significantly decreases GHG emissions, therefore indirectly supports ozone layer recovery. However, despite the overall environmental benefits associated with higher circular material use, recent assessments indicate that recycling processes themselves can contribute negatively to ozone depletion. This adverse effect arises from the recycling process itself, where environmental impacts can outweigh the benefits derived from avoided virgin polymer production or waste disposal. These findings suggest that, while an increase in the CMUR promotes resource efficiency and reduces pressure on primary materials, the environmental trade-offs within specific impact categories like ozone depletion must be carefully evaluated to ensure that circularity strategies do not inadvertently exacerbate planetary boundary transgressions (Tonini et al., 2021).

The CMUR has a direct positive impact on SDG 7, and indirect positive impacts on goals 8,9, and 12. Figure 2 illustrates the positive impacts of a high CMUR on both the planetary boundaries, as well as the SDGs. Drawing on Kate Raworth's doughnut economics concept, the figure consists of two concentric rings: the outer ring represents the ecological ceiling, here operationalised through the planetary boundaries, while the inner ring represents the social foundation, captured in this context by the SDGs.

Figure 2: Impacts of indicator 1 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 2: Recycling rate of municipal waste (percentage)

The recycling rate of municipal waste measures the share of recycled municipal waste in total municipal waste generation. Municipal waste recycling includes material recycling (e.g. paper, glass, plastics, and metal) composting (of organic waste like food), and anaerobic digestion (biological treatment of organic waste to produce biogas) (Eurostat, 2025a). Municipal waste includes household waste, waste from small businesses and public institutions, and similar waste collected by or on behalf of municipalities.

The municipal waste recycling rate reflects how effectively a country or region collects, processes, and reintegrates its waste into the economy.

The recycling rate of municipal solid waste (MSW) is formalised as:

Equation 2. The recycling rate of municipal waste (MSW)

$$\text{Recycling rate} = \frac{\text{total tonnes MSW recycled, composted}}{\text{total tonnes MSW recycled, composted, landfilled, incinerated}} \times 100$$

The above-mentioned formula does not consider exported waste. Reported recycling rates of MSW of EU Member States are therefore not directly comparable with those of waste generation.

A higher recycling rate signals better waste management practices, reduced landfill use, and progress toward circular economy goals. It also contributes to lowering greenhouse gas emissions, conserving resources, and reducing environmental pollution.

Policy-related performance threshold:

- Reaching 55% recycling of MSW by 2025, 60% by 2030, and 65% by 2035 → binding obligation to be met by all Member States (EU Waste Framework Directive).
- Reducing residual (i.e. non-recycled) municipal waste by 50% by 2030, which means halving the 2020 amount of 113 million tonnes to 56.5 million tonnes → non-binding commitment to be achieved at the EU level (Circular Economy Action Plan).
- Based on [EU population predictions](#) (452,835,710 people by 2030), the target for residual waste by 2030 is ca. **124.8 kg per capita per year**.

This indicator is a key benchmark for environmental performance.

The recycling rate is a measure of a downstream intervention in the economy's material flow. The "reduce, reuse, recycle" hierarchy of a circular economy suggests that a truly sustainable system would prioritise reduction and reuse first. It must be acknowledged that an over-emphasis on recycling can sometimes obscure the more fundamental problem of over-consumption. The second target of halving residual municipal waste is therefore critical as it represents an absolute target and not a relative one like the goals for the recycling rate. Even though the recycling rate in the EU increased from 45% in 2015 to 48% in 2020, the absolute amount of residual waste remained stable during that period, reflecting the offset of improvements in recycling rates by increases in waste generation (EEA, 2022). To achieve genuine progress towards circularity, policy frameworks should therefore place greater emphasis on absolute waste prevention, ensuring that efficiency gains from recycling are not undermined by growing material throughput.

The recycling rate of municipal waste has a direct positive impact on six of the nine planetary boundaries, and only an indirect positive or neutral impact on the three remaining boundaries, namely Stratospheric Ozone Depletion, Ocean Acidification, and Atmospheric Aerosol Loading.

Direct positive impacts:

- **Climate Change:** A high municipal waste recycling rate reduces the need for extracting and processing virgin materials, which are responsible for over 55% of global GHG emissions. By substituting virgin materials for secondary ones, the energy-intensive processes of mining, refining, and manufacturing are reduced, directly mitigating climate change (by lowering GHG emissions). Additionally, a high recycling rate has a positive impact on climate change by reducing methane emissions from landfills. When organic waste is composted or anaerobically digested instead of being landfilled, it prevents the anaerobic decomposition that produces methane.
- **Biogeochemical Flows:** Composting, a component of the recycling rate, directly contributes to closing the loop on nutrient cycles. Returning valuable nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus to the soil, it reduces the need for synthetic fertilisers, which are a primary driver of the transgression of this boundary.
- **Freshwater Change:** Producing materials from scratch is highly water intensive. Recycling municipal waste reduces the need for water in extraction and manufacturing, helping to preserve freshwater resources. Additionally, recycling and composting reduce the amount

of waste that ends up in landfills. This mitigates the formation of leachate, a toxic liquid that can contaminate groundwater and surface water. Composting also improves the soil's water retention capacity, further supporting the freshwater boundary.

- **Land-system Change:** Recycling lowers the demand for new raw materials, which in turn reduces land-use change caused by mining, agriculture, and landfill expansion. This helps protect forests and natural habitats. Furthermore, by diverting waste from landfills, a high recycling rate reduces the land area required for waste disposal.
- **Biosphere Integrity:** By limiting habitat destruction and pollution linked to virgin material extraction, recycling supports biodiversity conservation and reduces ecosystem degradation.
- **Novel Entities:** Recycling is a key strategy for managing novel entities, such as plastics, which are a major component of municipal waste. By keeping these materials in circulation, the recycling rate directly helps to reduce their leakage and accumulation in the environment, which is the primary cause of this boundary's transgression.

Indirect positive or neutral impacts:

- **Atmospheric Aerosol Loading:** While waste recycling can reduce industrial activity and fossil fuel combustion associated with virgin material production, thereby lowering emissions of particulate matter and other aerosols, the relationship is less direct and systemic than with the other planetary boundaries. The recycling process itself generates emissions, and because the indicator primarily reflects waste diversion, its influence on atmospheric aerosols remains relatively limited.
- **Ocean Acidification:** Recycling indirectly helps reduce ocean acidification by decreasing fossil fuel consumption (given that recycling efforts are not offset by increased total waste generation). Less energy-intensive material production means fewer CO₂ emissions, which are the main driver of acidification in marine ecosystems.
- **Stratospheric Ozone Depletion:** Similar to the circular material use rate, a high recycling rate may reduce GHG emissions (especially methane from landfills), which indirectly supports ozone recovery by mitigating stratospheric cooling. However, depending on the GHG emissions produced during recycling processes and the associated environmental trade-offs, increased recycling activity could also inadvertently contribute to ozone depletion.

The recycling rate of municipal waste has a direct positive impact on SDGs 2,4,6,7, and 8 and an indirect positive impact on goal 9. Figure 3 illustrates the positive impacts of a high municipal waste recycling rate on both the planetary boundaries, as well as the SDGs.

Figure 3: Impacts of indicator 2 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: own elaboration

Indicators 3 and 4: Total generated biowaste and total recovered biowaste (kilo tonnes dry)

The total generated biowaste indicator captures the amount of biowaste generated annually by households and industry, within a specific region - typically expressed in tonnes per year or kilograms per capita. Biowaste includes food waste (from households, restaurants, food processing), garden and park waste (grass clippings, leaves, branches), and other organic biodegradable waste from municipal sources, such as paper and cardboard waste. The total recovered biowaste measures how much of the generated biowaste is successfully reused, recycled, or composted. They are metrics used by the EU to monitor progress towards sustainable waste management and circular economic goals. EU countries and cities use these indicators to evaluate and improve their waste strategies. While the generation of biowaste is inevitable in any society, tracking this indicator allows policymakers and other relevant stakeholders to assess the efficiency of upstream systems, such as food supply chains and consumption habits. High-quality data on biowaste generation and recovery helps identify opportunities for waste prevention.

Policy-related target:

- Separate collection of bio-waste.

According to the EU Directive (EU) 2018/851, commonly known as the New Waste Framework Directive (WFD), included in the “Circular Economy Package” mandates the introduction of a separate collection of bio-waste as of January 1, 2024, updating article 22 of the WFD, making this indicator increasingly important for tracking compliance and performance. This legal obligation acts as a threshold for compliance and monitoring. Another relevant indicator, currently under discussion, is potential legally binding targets for biowaste capture. According to the Bio-based Industry Consortium (BIC) and Zero Waste Europe, the theoretical for biowaste generation in the EU is around 60 million tonnes/year, but only around 26% is currently captured. Although organisations such as Zero Waste Europe have called for binding targets, the EU currently does not have any legally binding recycling targets specifically for biowaste (Favoino et al., 2020).

The total generated biowaste and total recovered biowaste can have a positive direct impact on four boundaries. They also exert indirect positive effects on the remaining five.

Direct positive impacts:

- **Climate Change:** Efficient biowaste recovery significantly reduces methane emissions from landfills, a potent greenhouse gas. When organic waste is composted or digested anaerobically, it not only avoids harmful emissions but also produces renewable energy in the form of biogas. These practices directly support climate mitigation efforts and help stabilise atmospheric carbon levels (Kern et al., 2012).
- **Biogeochemical Flows:** Biowaste contains valuable nutrients that, when recovered properly, can be returned to soils through compost or digestate. This reduces the need for synthetic fertilisers, which often lead to nutrient overload in water bodies. By closing nutrient loops, biowaste recovery directly supports the balance of nitrogen and phosphorus cycles (Drosg et al., 2015).
- **Land-system Change:** Recovering biowaste reduces the pressure on landfills and incinerators, freeing up land for more sustainable uses. Moreover, composted biowaste enhances soil health, reducing the need for land-intensive agricultural expansion. These effects directly contribute to preserving natural landscapes and minimising land-system disruption (Kern et al., 2012).
- **Biosphere Integrity:** Healthy soils enriched with organic matter from recovered biowaste support diverse microbial and plant life. By avoiding pollution from mismanaged waste and promoting regenerative practices, biowaste recovery directly strengthens ecosystem resilience and biodiversity, key components of biosphere integrity.

Indirect positive or neutral impacts:

- **Ocean Acidification:** Although biowaste management does not directly regulate freshwater withdrawal, it indirectly supports this boundary by reducing the demand for water-intensive synthetic fertilisers. Additionally, proper composting and digestion prevent leachate contamination, helping maintain clean water systems.
- **Freshwater Change:** Producing materials from scratch is highly water intensive. Recycling municipal waste reduces the need for water in extraction and manufacturing, helping to preserve freshwater resources.

- **Novel Entities:** Biowaste recovery systems that enforce purity standards help prevent contamination from microplastics and hazardous chemicals. Though not directly targeting novel entities, these systems indirectly reduce the spread of persistent pollutants into soils and food chains.
- **Atmospheric Aerosol Loading:** Avoiding open burning and uncontrolled disposal of biowaste reduces particulate emissions that contribute to aerosol loading. While not a primary driver, well-managed biowaste systems indirectly improve air quality and reduce the release of harmful airborne particles.
- **Stratospheric Ozone Depletion:** While biowaste itself does not contain ozone-depleting substances, avoiding incineration of contaminated organic waste helps prevent the release of harmful compounds. In this way, biowaste recovery indirectly supports the protection of the ozone layer through cleaner waste practices.

The indicators are included in the EU-BMS and contribute to European Green Deal objectives, notably: 2.1.3. Mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy. They have an indirect positive impact on SDG 12 (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Impacts of indicators 3 and 4 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 5: Energy productivity

Energy productivity is a measure of how efficiently an economy uses energy to generate economic value. It is calculated as the ratio of gross domestic product (GDP) to energy consumption. A higher energy productivity means that less energy is required to produce a unit of economic value, which is an indicator of efficient and sustainable energy use. Governments use this indicator to track progress towards energy efficiency goals.

Energy productivity quantifies the economic output generated per unit of energy consumed. It is measured in Euro per kilogram of oil equivalent (EUR/ kg. oil-eq.) and is formalised as:

Equation 3. Energy productivity

$$\text{Energy productivity} = \frac{GDP}{\text{gross available energy}}$$

Policy-related performance threshold:

- Reducing EU final energy consumption by at least 11.7% in 2030 compared to the 2020 projections for energy use → this translates to a primary energy consumption of 992.5 million tonnes of oil equivalent (Mtoe) and a final energy consumption target of 763 Mtoe (EU Energy Efficiency Directive)
- Based on EU population predictions, this would mean a target of **2.192 toe per capita per year (~25,500 kWh/person)** for primary energy consumption and **1.685 toe per capita per year (~19,600 kWh/person)** for final energy consumption by 2030.

Energy is essential for every economic activity, whether a production process or a service provision, yet there are physical limits to how far energy efficiency can be improved. Decoupling describes the relationship between economic growth and energy use. When the amount of energy consumed per unit of GDP decreases, but total energy consumption still rises due to expanding economic activity, this is referred to as relative decoupling. In contrast, absolute decoupling occurs when total energy consumption declines even as the economy continues to grow, representing a more sustainable trajectory. However, the indicator of energy productivity measures only efficiency and does not differentiate between energy sources. While decoupling is still important even if the entire energy used is renewable, it is even more critical when the energy is mainly fossil-fuel-based. Thus, a significant benefit is only achieved when increased productivity is combined with a strategic transition to renewable energy sources, a factor not inherently captured by the indicator. A country could increase energy productivity by becoming more efficient but still rely on a fossil-fuel-dominated grid, resulting in only a partial and limited improvement in relation to the planetary boundaries. For the subsequent discussion of the indicator's impacts on the planetary boundaries, we assume an economy that relies primarily on fossil fuels, reflecting the current situation in the EU, where fossil fuels account for more than two-thirds of the gross available energy supply. Energy productivity has a direct positive impact on four of the nine planetary boundaries and an indirect one on two further ones.

Direct positive impacts:

- **Climate Change:** A higher energy productivity ensures that GDP growth is increasingly decoupled from energy consumption, particularly from fossil fuels. Since the burning of fossil fuels for energy is the primary source of GHGs, this decoupling directly limits the

volume of GHG emissions required per unit of economic output, providing deep structural mitigation against climate change.

- **Ocean Acidification:** Ocean acidification is a direct consequence of the ocean absorbing atmospheric CO₂. By increasing energy productivity, the economy reduces the fossil fuel consumption needed to sustain its growth, directly lessening the CO₂ pressure on the atmosphere and oceans, mitigating acidification. The positive effect of an increased energy productivity on this boundary is highly dependent on the energy source and should be reevaluated for different energy mixes.
- **Land-system Change:** Energy infrastructure, including mines, gas pipelines, hydropower dams, and large renewable farms, requires extensive land-system conversion. Decoupling economic value from total energy demand can therefore reduce the need for this physical expansion, decreasing the pressure on natural land systems, forests, and wetlands. However, a substantial benefit for this planetary boundary is only realised under conditions of absolute decoupling, rather than relative decoupling.
- **Atmospheric Aerosol Loading:** Fossil fuel combustion is a major source of atmospheric aerosols. A higher energy productivity that decreases the total amount of energy used (absolute decoupling) directly reduces the fossil fuel consumption needed for economic activity and thus the release of aerosols into the atmosphere.

Indirect positive impacts:

- **Freshwater Change:** Improved energy productivity can indirectly benefit freshwater resources by reducing overall energy demand per GDP unit, which in turn decreases water consumption for cooling and other processes in the energy sector. This effect is critical even for low-carbon sources like nuclear power, which still require substantial cooling water.
- **Biosphere Integrity:** By reducing the overall energy footprint required per unit of economic output, higher energy productivity can mitigate habitat destruction, land degradation, and ecosystem fragmentation associated with energy extraction, infrastructure development, and resource transport. When combined with a transition to low-impact renewable energy sources, improved energy productivity can therefore help preserve biodiversity, maintain ecosystem functions, and support the overall integrity and resilience of the biosphere.

A high energy productivity has a direct positive impact on SDGs 2,4,6, and 7 and an indirect positive impact on goal 11. Figure 5 illustrates the positive impacts of a high energy productivity on both the planetary boundaries, as well as the SDGs.

Figure 5: Impacts of indicator 5 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 6: Total food waste generation along supply chain (t/person)

This indicator measures the total amount of food that goes unsold or unused across all stages of the supply chain, from the farm to the consumer, expressed in tonnes per person. It represents a measure of the inefficiency and waste embedded in the global food system.

In 2015, the United Nations defined target 12.3 on food waste as part of SDG 12, which calls for halving per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reducing food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses, by 2030. In 2022, 1.05 billion tonnes of food were wasted globally, of which 60% stemmed from households, equating to a third of all food produced for human consumption and more than a billion meals wasted per day. In the EU, ca. 132kg per capita of food is wasted annually, totalling over 59 million tonnes. 54% of the food waste is generated by households, while the remaining 46% is generated upwards in the food supply chain, during primary production and the manufacture of food and beverages, by restaurants, or in the retail and distribution of food (UN, 2025).

Policy-related performance threshold:

By the end of 2030,

- Reducing per capita global food waste at the retail and consumption level by 30%.
- Reducing food losses in processing and manufacturing by 10% ([EU WFD](#)).

Food waste generation has a direct positive impact on five of the planetary boundaries because wasting food means wasting all the emissions and resources used to produce it: land, water, and fertilisers (EC, 2025).

Direct positive impacts:

- **Climate Change:** The global food system is responsible for approximately 30% of global anthropogenic GHG emissions. When food is wasted, all the GHGs from its production, processing, transport, and storage are also wasted. Half of total anthropogenic methane emissions are linked to livestock and paddy rice cultivation, while nitrogen fertilisers used in agriculture are responsible for three-quarters of total N₂O emissions. Furthermore, food waste in landfills releases methane. Reducing food waste, therefore, directly mitigates these emissions.
- **Biogeochemical Flows:** The excessive use of agricultural fertilisers is a major driver of the disruption of the nitrogen and phosphorus cycles. Reducing food waste lessens the demand for food production, which in turn decreases the usage of synthetic fertilisers.
- **Freshwater Change:** Agriculture is the single largest consumer of freshwater resources, with up to 70% of the world's freshwater used in the sector. Reducing food waste directly conserves the resource.
- **Land-System Change:** The food system drives 80-90% of tropical deforestation and wetland loss. A reduction in food waste lowers the demand for new agricultural land, thereby protecting forests, wetlands, and other natural habitats from conversion.
- **Biosphere Integrity:** Food systems are responsible for two-thirds of biosphere integrity loss, with some estimates suggesting the figure could be as high as 80%. Agriculture, aquaculture, and fisheries are threats to 63% of all species, identified to be at risk of extinction. Expanding agricultural activities directly leads to habitat destruction and fragmentation. Reducing food waste, therefore, plays a pivotal role in alleviating these pressures, as lower demand for agricultural output translates into reduced land conversion.

The indicator is indirectly linked to SDG 12. Figure 6 illustrates the positive impacts of a reduced food waste generation on both the planetary boundaries, as well as the SDGs.

Figure 6: Impacts of indicator 6 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 7: Resource productivity (EUR/kg)

Resource productivity measures the total amount of natural resources used (e.g. materials directly used) by an economy and is operationalised as the ratio of GDP to domestic material consumption (DMC) and measured in EUR/kg. It helps assess whether an economy is becoming more efficient in its use of resources over time. Resource productivity is included in the EU Circular Economy Monitoring Framework and is formalised as:

Equation 4. Resource productivity

$$\text{Resource productivity} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{kg}} \right] = \frac{\text{GDP}}{\text{DMC}}$$

where $\text{DMC} = \text{Domestic extraction} + \text{Imports} - \text{Exports}$

It is important to note that DMC reflects **apparent consumption**, not final consumption, and excludes upstream resource flows associated with imports and exports.

In 2024, the aggregate resource productivity in the EU amounted to 3€/kg. Since the year 2000, resource productivity in the EU has increased by ca. 52%. During that period, some Member States experienced an increase in GDP while significantly decreasing their DMC, indicating absolute decoupling, while others achieved only relative decoupling as their DMC increased but more slowly than their GDP. Some other Member States had higher DMC growth than GWP growth and thus did not decouple at all (Eurostat, 2025b).

The DMC is defined as the annual quantity of raw materials extracted from the domestic territory, plus all physical imports minus all physical exports. However, since not all materials used in production appear in the product, resources like water which are required in large quantities in many manufacturing processes are not included in the DMC (Eurostat, n.d.). The DMC index, therefore, does not cover dislocated environmental pressures caused by the outsourcing of material-intensive production processes to other parts of the world. This limitation challenges the assumption that resource use has been successfully decoupled from economic growth at the EU level between 2000 and 2024. Additionally, Malatyinszki et al. (2025) found that the numerator and denominator of the fraction are not independent of each other, thus further undermining the representativeness and quality of the indicator, as it greatly simplifies sustainability assessments. On the other hand, the volume of reused materials is added back into the DMC calculation, causing the material consumption metric to rise even when circularity improves. Waste recycling affects DMC through a similar accounting mechanism, contributing to a perceived increase in material consumption. The indicator resource productivity has a direct positive impact on seven of the nine planetary boundaries, and only an indirect positive or neutral impact on the two remaining boundaries, namely stratospheric ozone depletion and novel entities.

Direct positive impacts:

- **Climate Change:** High resource productivity means more economic value is generated per unit of material used - reducing demand for virgin sources, which drive over 70% of global GHG emissions (Circularity Gap Report 2023). By minimising extraction and energy-intensive processing, resource productivity directly lowers emissions.
- **Biosphere Integrity:** The extraction and processing of materials are linked to up to 90% of land-use-related biodiversity loss (Oberle et al., 2019). Decoupling the economy from material consumption and improving resource productivity helps mitigate biodiversity loss.
- **Biogeochemical Flows:** Material consumption, particularly from agriculture and industrial processes, is a major driver of nutrient pollution and the disruption of the nitrogen and phosphorus cycles. A higher resource productivity, by reducing the overall material footprint, helps to alleviate this pressure.
- **Freshwater Change:** The extraction and processing of materials, from mining to agriculture, are major drivers of freshwater consumption. By decoupling economic growth from material use, higher resource productivity lowers water demand across supply chains. More efficient production processes, particularly in water-intensive sectors such as agriculture, textiles, and manufacturing, help relieve pressure on freshwater systems and support the stability of the freshwater change boundary.
- **Land-system Change:** Resource extraction and processing are major drivers of land degradation, deforestation, and urbanisation. By generating more economic value with fewer material inputs, higher resource productivity reduces the need for land-intensive activities such as mining, agriculture, and infrastructure expansion. This alleviates pressure on land, limits habitat conversion and soil degradation, and supports sustainable land management, thereby helping to maintain the ecological functions critical to the land-system change boundary.
- **Atmospheric Aerosol Loading:** Higher resource productivity reduces the need for energy-intensive extraction, manufacturing, and transportation processes, which are major sources of particulate emissions. By using fewer materials to produce the same economic output, industries emit less soot, dust, and other aerosols that contribute to air pollution and climate forcing. This efficiency helps lower the release of harmful airborne particles, supporting the stability of the atmospheric aerosol loading boundary.
- **Ocean Acidification:** Higher resource productivity reduces the demand for carbon-intensive production and energy use, which in turn lowers CO₂ emissions, the primary driver

of ocean acidification. By using fewer materials to achieve the same economic output, industries and supply chains emit less carbon, helping to stabilise ocean pH levels and protect marine ecosystems from the harmful effects of acidification.

Indirect positive impacts:

- **Stratospheric Ozone Depletion:** Similar to the circular material use rate, an improved resource productivity may reduce GHG emissions through the decreased production and consumption of materials, which indirectly supports ozone recovery by mitigating stratospheric cooling. However, depending on the GHG emissions produced during recycling processes and the associated environmental trade-offs, increased recycling activity could also inadvertently contribute to ozone depletion.
- **Novel Entities:** Higher resource productivity may reduce the generation and use of hazardous chemicals by promoting cleaner production and lower material throughput. Yet, unless paired with targeted chemical management, the reduction in pollution is not guaranteed, hence the impact is indirect but potentially positive.

Resource productivity is indirectly linked to SDGs 8,11, and 12. Figure 7 illustrates the positive impacts of a high resource productivity on both the planetary boundaries, as well as the SDGs.

Figure 7: Impacts of indicator 7 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 8: Biomass share in domestic material consumption (percentage)

The domestic material consumption (biomass share, %) expresses in percentage terms the proportion of biomass in the total domestic material consumption (DMC) of an economy. The biomass share reflects how much of a country's material use is based on renewable biological resources. A higher biomass share may indicate a shift towards renewable and potentially more sustainable resource use, especially if managed responsibly. However, excessive biomass extraction (e.g., deforestation, overharvesting) can still harm ecosystems, so this indicator must be interpreted alongside biodiversity and land-use metrics.

Equation 5. Biomass share

$$\text{Biomass share} = \frac{\text{Biomass}}{\text{DMC}}$$

where $\text{DMC} = \text{Domestic extraction} + \text{Imports} - \text{Exports}$

DMC represents the total amount of materials directly used by an economy and is calculated as the sum of four material categories: biomass, metal ores, non-metallic minerals, and fossil energy materials and carriers. It includes domestic extraction plus imports, minus exports.

By focusing on the biomass share of DMC, this indicator provides insight into the relative importance of bio-based resources within the overall material mix of national economies. Monitoring the role of biomass is crucial for assessing progress towards a more sustainable, bio-based, and resource-efficient economy (D2.4 SUSTRACK). The indicator is part of Eurostat's Economy-Wide Material Flow Accounts (EW-MFA), which offer a comprehensive overview of material flows into and out of economies.

A higher biomass share reflects a greater substitution of virgin fossil materials for renewable ones, thereby contributing to the reduction of environmental pressures associated with fossil resource extraction. Several EU regulations and policy frameworks address biomass use, though none currently set a mandatory minimum share of biomass in Domestic Material Consumption (DMC). However, biomass targets are embedded in renewable energy and sustainability directives. For example, the Renewable Energy Directive III (RED III) (EU 2023/2413) sets a binding target for EU countries to reach at least 42,5% renewable energy in final energy consumption by 2023, with biomass playing a key role.

Although currently no fixed % threshold for biomass in DMC exists yet, the EU aims to expand biomass use to replace fossil inputs in energy and materials (EU Bioeconomy strategy). However, thresholds should be context-specific, considering national resource availability, ecosystem health and competing land uses. The use of sustainable bio-based products is promoted through the use of voluntary standards and certifications. These frameworks aim to increase the share of renewable materials in products while ensuring transparency and sustainability.

The indicator Biomass share in domestic material consumption (DMC) has a direct positive impact on three of the nine planetary boundaries, and only an indirect positive or neutral impact on the other six boundaries.

Direct positive impacts:

- **Climate Change:** A high share of bio-based materials in domestic material consumption contributes directly to climate change mitigation by replacing fossil-based resources with

renewable biological inputs. When these materials are sustainably sourced, such as through responsible forestry, regenerative agriculture, or organic waste recovery, they offer a lower carbon footprint across their life cycle. This shift not only decouples economic activity from fossil carbon but also supports long-term carbon sequestration in soils and biomass, reinforcing the stability of the climate boundary.

- **Biogeochemical Flows:** A higher biomass share supports nutrient cycling by returning organic matter, like composted food and crop residues, to soils. This reduces reliance on synthetic fertilisers, lowering nitrogen and phosphorus runoff and helping stabilise this boundary.

Indirect positive or neutral impacts:

- **Stratospheric Ozone Depletion:** Biomass use does not directly affect ozone-depleting substances. However, if increased biomass share leads to a reduction in fossil-based industrial production, there may be an indirect decrease in the use or emission of these harmful substances. Still, this effect is marginal and highly dependent on the sectors involved.
- **Ocean Acidification:** Biomass-based materials, when used to replace fossil-based inputs, contribute to lower CO₂ emissions, especially if they are part of long-lived products or circular systems. This substitution offers an indirect positive effect by helping stabilise ocean chemistry, though the impact depends on the scale and sustainability of biomass sourcing.
- **Novel Entities:** Bio-based products may reduce the use of synthetic chemicals, plastics, and persistent pollutants, offering a potentially positive indirect effect on this boundary. However, the benefit depends on how biomass is processed, some bio-based materials still involve hazardous additives, solvents, or treatments. Without strict controls and green chemistry principles, biomass use could still contribute to chemical pollution.
- **Atmospheric Aerosol Loading:** Biomass combustion or processing can emit particulate matter and aerosols, which affect air quality and climate. This presents a mixed indirect impact: while biomass may reduce fossil fuel use, it can also introduce new sources of aerosols unless clean technologies like advanced combustion systems or filters are used. The net effect depends on the method and scale of biomass utilisation.

Indirect mixed impacts:

- **Land-system Change:** Biomass share in DMC has a mixed impact on Land-system change. It can be positive if biomass is sourced sustainably and used efficiently, but it can be negative if it drives land conversion or ecosystem degradation. Therefore, it should be assessed alongside land-use policies, biodiversity metrics, and sourcing standards.
- **Biosphere Integrity:** Biomass can support biodiversity when sourced sustainably, such as from residues or certified forestry. However, intensive monocultures and land conversion for biomass production can fragment habitats and reduce species diversity, making the impact highly context dependent.
- **Freshwater Change:** Biomass production, particularly for crops, bioenergy, or industrial feedstocks, can place significant pressure on freshwater resources. Irrigated biomass crops like sugarcane or cotton require large volumes of water, potentially exacerbating water scarcity in vulnerable regions. The impact of biomass share on this boundary is indirect and context dependent, varying with crop type, climate, and agricultural practices. Sustainable sourcing and rainfed systems can mitigate these pressures.

This indicator directly contributes to SDGs 2,4,6,7,8, and 9. Figure 8 illustrates the positive impacts of a high share of biomass in a domestic material consumption on both the planetary boundaries, as well as the SDGs.

Figure 8: Impacts of indicator 8 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 9: Gross final energy consumption renewable share (percentage)

The indicator gross final energy consumption renewable share (%) measures the proportion of total energy consumed by end users that comes from renewable sources like solar, wind, hydro, biomass, and geothermal. It reflects progress towards sustainable energy systems and climate goals. The indicator supports climate mitigation by reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

Equation 6. Renewable share

$$\text{Renewable share} = \frac{\text{Renewable energy consumption}}{\text{Gross final energy consumption}}$$

The share of renewable energy indicator reflects the energy transition toward low-carbon systems and helps assess national and EU-level targets (e.g., 42.5% by 2030 under RED III). The indicator is used to monitor compliance with the EU RED III.

By focusing on the renewable share of gross final energy consumption, this indicator provides insight into the transition towards low-carbon energy systems and the growing role of renewables in national energy mixes. Monitoring the uptake of renewable energy is essential for assessing

progress towards climate neutrality, energy security, and sustainable development goals. The indicator is part of Eurostat’s energy statistics framework and aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG 7.2.1), which promotes access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all.

A higher renewable share reflects a greater substitution of fossil-based energy sources with renewables such as wind, solar, hydro, geothermal, and sustainably sourced biomass. This shift contributes to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, air pollution, and environmental degradation associated with fossil fuel extraction and combustion. Several EU regulations and policy instruments directly support this transition. Most notably, the Renewable Energy Directive III (RED III) (EU 2023/2413) sets a binding target for Member States to achieve at least 42.5% renewable energy in gross final consumption by 2030, with an aspirational goal of reaching 45%.

Policy-related performance threshold:

- Achieving a minimum of 42.5% renewable energy in the energy mix by 2030.

Although no universal threshold applies to all sectors or regions, the EU encourages differentiated targets based on national capabilities, resource availability, and energy demand profiles. The integration of renewables is further supported through voluntary certification schemes, grid access reforms, and investment incentives. These frameworks aim to accelerate the deployment of clean energy technologies while ensuring system reliability and sustainability.

The indicator has a direct positive impact on the Climate Change planetary boundary and contributes indirectly to several others by reducing emissions and pollutants associated with fossil energy systems. Its influence depends on the type of renewable energy deployed and the scale of substitution.

Direct positive direct impacts:

- **Climate Change:** Replacing fossil fuels with renewable energy sources, such as wind, solar, hydro, geothermal, and sustainably sourced bioenergy, reduces greenhouse gas emissions across electricity, heating, and transport sectors. This directly mitigates climate change and supports decarbonization targets.
- **Ocean Acidification:** Lower CO₂ emissions from renewables help stabilise ocean pH levels, reducing acidification stress on marine ecosystems.
- **Atmospheric Aerosol Loading:** Renewables like wind and solar emit negligible particulates compared to fossil fuels. This improves air quality and reduces aerosol-related climate and health impacts.

Indirect positive or neutral impacts:

- **Biogeochemical Flows:** Reduced fossil fuel use lowers nitrogen and sulphur emissions from combustion, easing pressure on nutrient cycles. Bioenergy may contribute positively if organic residues are returned to soils, but this depends on land use and agricultural practices.
- **Novel Entities (Chemical Pollution):** Transitioning to renewables reduces emissions of heavy metals, hydrocarbons, and persistent organic pollutants associated with fossil fuel extraction, refining, and combustion.

- **Stratospheric Ozone Depletion (Neutral):** Renewable energy systems do not emit ozone-depleting substances. While the impact is minimal, reduced industrial activity linked to fossil fuels may offer marginal benefits.

Indirect Mixed Impacts

- **Land-system Change:** Large-scale deployment of bioenergy or hydropower can alter land use, affect soil integrity, and disrupt ecosystems. In contrast, solar and wind have relatively low land footprints when sited responsibly.
- **Biosphere Integrity** Renewable energy can reduce habitat loss and pollution from fossil extraction. However, poorly planned installations, such as large dams or monoculture bioenergy plantations, may fragment habitats and harm biodiversity.
- **Freshwater Change:** Some renewables (e.g., bioenergy, hydropower) require significant water for cultivation or cooling. Others (e.g., wind, solar PV) have minimal water footprints, making the impact highly technology- and location-dependent.

This indicator directly contributes to SDGs 2,4,6,7,8,12 and 13 and indirectly to goal 11. Figure 9 illustrates the positive impacts of a high share of renewable energy in the energy mix on both the planetary boundaries, as well as the SDGs.

Figure 9: Impacts of indicator 9 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

3.2.2. Environmental performance of the bio-based economy

This category includes ten indicators, seven of which serve the shared purpose of assessing GHG emission intensities, which are defined as GHG emissions per unit of economic activity or output, and are organised according to economic sector, as classified by NACE codes. Although the primary contribution of these indicators lies in addressing the planetary boundary of climate change, the broader environmental pressures exerted by each sector call for a comprehensive analysis across all planetary boundaries.

Emission intensities can be calculated for any pollutant(s), like CO₂, SO₂, NO_x, or, in this case, GHGs, and are expressed as:

Equation 7. Emission intensity

$$\text{Emission intensity} = \frac{\text{amount of pollutant released}}{\text{amount of activity responsible for the release}}$$

The GHG emission intensity indicators selected in SUSTRACK are presented in Table 2 below. These indicators are compiled under Eurostat's Air Emission Accounts (AEA), which allocate national emissions to economic activities according to the NACE Rev. 2 classification and are consistent with the National Accounts framework.

- A decline in GHG intensity may indicate improvements in energy efficiency, fuel switching toward renewables, process optimisation, or electrification.
- An increase may reflect higher fossil energy use, production of more energy-intensive products, or reduced economic output.

Table 2: GHG emission intensity indicators

Indicator Group	NACE code	Indicator name
Primary production	A01: Agriculture	GHG emission intensities by agriculture
	A02: Forestry and Logging	GHG emission intensities by forestry and logging
	A03: Fishing and Aquaculture	GHG emission intensities by fishing and aquaculture
Manufacturing	C10-C12: Food, Beverage, Tobacco	GHG emission intensities by the food, beverage, and tobacco industries
	C13-C15: Textiles	GHG emission intensities from textiles
	C16: Wood products	GHG emission intensities from wood products, except furniture
	C17: Paper and Paper products	GHG emission intensities from paper and paper products

GHG emission intensity targets for these sectors are predominantly driven by the EU's commitment to achieving climate neutrality by 2050 and the intermediate target of a 90% net GHG reduction

by 2040 (relative to 1990 levels). A key legislative framework that regulates GHG emissions in the EU is the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS). Another key policy instrument is the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR), which, together with the Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation, ensures comprehensive coverage of emissions across all major sectors of the economy.

Under the ESR, the agriculture sector (NACE A01) and smaller industrial emitters within manufacturing are assigned binding national emission reduction targets that apply outside the scope of the ETS. The ESR mandates a collective EU-wide reduction of emissions in these sectors, requiring several Member States to intensify their mitigation efforts to meet the 2030 and 2040 goals.

The forestry and logging sector (NACE A02) is regulated through the LULUCF framework, which addresses emissions and removals from land use and land-use change. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) estimates that the broader AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use) sector contributes approximately 13-21% of global net anthropogenic GHG emissions. Within this sector, reducing deforestation offers the greatest immediate potential for emission reduction, while enhancing carbon sequestration through sustainable forest and soil management provides significant long-term mitigation benefits.

The manufacturing sector (NACE C10-C17) is subject to both the EU ETS and the ESR, depending on the scale and energy intensity of operations. Larger, energy-intensive facilities, such as those involved in the production of steel, cement, glass, pulp, paper, and chemicals, fall under the ETS, while smaller installations are regulated by the ESR. These frameworks compel industries to pursue energy efficiency, process innovation, and low-carbon technologies as part of the EU's broader decarbonisation pathway.

The EU ETS, launched in 2005 as the world's first carbon market, remains the cornerstone of the EU's climate policy. It operates on the "cap-and-trade" principle, requiring polluters to pay for their emissions and thereby creating a financial incentive to reduce them. The ETS currently covers approximately 40% of the EU's total GHG emissions and applies to activities including electricity and heat generation, heavy industrial manufacturing, and aviation within the European Economic Area, as well as maritime transport, added to the system in 2024. The scheme also regulates emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) from energy production and industry, nitrous oxide (N₂O) from chemical manufacturing, and perfluorocarbons (PFCs) from aluminium production. Participation in the ETS is mandatory for operators within these sectors, though smaller installations may be excluded if equivalent national measures are implemented.

Policy-related thresholds:

- Achieving a 90% net GHG reduction by 2040 (relative to 1990 levels) and reaching climate neutrality by 2050.
- ETS, ESR, and LULUCF frameworks establish a multi-sectoral architecture for emission reduction across the EU.

The following section addresses the overall effects of reducing GHG emission intensities across all economic sectors on the planetary boundaries.

Direct positive impact:

- **Climate Change:** Reducing GHG emission intensities contributes directly to the management of the climate change boundary by cutting emissions of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O per unit of economic activity.
- **Ocean Acidification:** As ocean acidification is directly caused by the absorption of excess atmospheric CO₂, reducing the CO₂ intensity of any sector inherently mitigates the primary driver of this boundary's transgression.
- **Atmospheric Aerosol Loading:** Industrial combustion and energy use, which are usually large contributors to a sector's GHG emission intensity, are also major sources of particulate matter, sulphur dioxide, and nitrogen oxides. Reducing combustion related GHG emissions directly lowers aerosol loading (EPA, 2025).

While the planetary boundaries of Climate Change, Ocean Acidification, and Atmospheric Aerosol Loading are universally affected by reductions in GHG emission intensities across all sectors, the following explores the specific impacts of the individual indicators on the remaining six planetary boundaries.

Indicator 10: GHG emission intensities by agriculture (NACE 01)

Direct positive impacts:

- **Biogeochemical Flows:** The agricultural sector, specifically crop-livestock production systems, is the largest cause of human alteration of the nitrogen and phosphorus cycles. If GHG emission intensity reductions in the sector are due to an optimised fertiliser use and an alternative management of livestock production systems, which better integrates animal manure in crop production and matches N and P supply to livestock requirements, can have major positive impacts on this planetary boundary (Bouwman et al., 2013).
- **Freshwater Change:** Agriculture consumes up to 70% of the world's freshwater (UNESCO, 2024). Reductions in GHG emission intensity within the sector, often driven by improved efficiency and technological advancements, such as optimised irrigation systems, can alleviate pressure on the freshwater boundary by lowering overall water use. It is also important to note that certain water-saving innovations, such as solar-powered reverse osmosis for producing irrigation water from saline sources, may not be directly reflected in a reduced GHG emission intensity for NACE 01, but still significantly contribute to mitigating freshwater depletion. Such practices should, therefore, be acknowledged as complementary strategies in safeguarding this planetary boundary (Ingrao et al., 2023).
- **Land-system Change:** Agricultural expansion is a major driver of deforestation and land degradation. Reducing GHG emission intensities often relies on yield improvements and greater land efficiency, thus mitigating the pressure to convert natural ecosystems to cropland. Another key strategy is the reduction of food waste and the adoption of cascading use principles, ensuring that agricultural biomass is used efficiently across food, feed, material, and energy applications. This decreases the demand for additional land, while supporting circularity within the bioeconomy (Verburg et al., 2013).
- **Biosphere Integrity:** Agriculture, but especially food production, is the primary driver of biodiversity loss, contributing to both genetic diversity loss (measured by extinction rates) and functional diversity decline (reflected in the biodiversity intactness index). Reducing GHG emission intensities in agriculture often involves practices such as precision fertilisation, reduced chemical inputs, agroecology, and conservation tillage. These approaches help limit habitat conversion, decrease nutrient pollution, and maintain soil biodiversity and ecosystem functions. By minimising the pressures that lead to habitat

fragmentation, species decline, and ecosystem degradation, lower GHG emission intensities can alleviate agriculture’s contribution to the transgression of the biosphere integrity boundary. Sustainable agricultural practices that reduce emissions and enhance land stewardship are therefore essential not only for climate mitigation but also for safeguarding biodiversity (UNEP, 2021), (Campbell et al., 2017).

Indicator 10 has an indirect positive impact on SDGs 6,8,12,13, and 15. Figure 10 illustrates the positive impacts of a reduced GHG emission intensity by agriculture on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs.

Figure 10: Impacts of indicator 10 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 11: GHG emission intensities by forestry and logging (NACE A02)

Direct positive impacts:

- Land-system Change:** Lowering GHG emission intensity in the forestry sector supports the land-system change boundary by promoting the preservation of intact forests and reducing the carbon impact of timber harvesting. Sustainably managed forests help maintain the Earth’s land carbon sink, responsible for absorbing around one-third of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions since 1850, and preserve the regulatory functions forests provide for climate, water cycles, and biodiversity. By decreasing pressures that lead to deforestation and forest degradation, reduced GHG intensity also limits the conversion of natural ecosystems to high-emission land uses, thereby helping maintain forest cover closer to its Holocene

baseline and mitigating feedback loops such as those threatening the Amazon (Tomalka et al., 2024).

- **Biosphere Integrity:** Forests host about 80% of global biodiversity. Mitigation measures in the forestry sector, such as reducing deforestation and enhancing carbon sequestration, provide the largest share of LULUCF mitigation potential while protecting biodiversity (EC, n.d.).

Indicator 11 has an indirect positive impact on SDGs 6,8,12,13, and 15. Figure 11 illustrates the positive impacts of a reduced GHG emission intensity by forestry and logging on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs.

Figure 11: Impacts of indicator 11 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 12: GHG emission intensities by fishing and aquaculture (NACE A03)

Indirect positive impact:

- **Novel Entities:** The fishing industry is a major source of marine plastics like discarded fishing gear, contributing directly to the transgression of the novel entities boundary in the marine environment. Reducing GHG intensity does not inherently address the plastic pollution issue, unless combined with sustainable fishing practices.

Mixed impact:

- Biosphere Integrity:** While lower GHG emission intensities in fisheries and aquaculture can reduce fuel use and ease pressure on biosphere integrity, their overall impact remains mixed. Unsustainable practices, such as overfishing, habitat destruction (e.g. trawling, mangrove loss), nutrient pollution and disease transfer from intensive aquaculture, continue to drive loss of aquatic biodiversity and functional ecosystem decline. However, when emission reductions are achieved through sustainable methods, they can support biosphere integrity. Approaches such as Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA), which recycles nutrients within the farmed ecosystem, and restoration aquaculture, which actively restores habitats like oyster reefs or seaweed forests, can enhance water quality, biodiversity, and carbon sequestration. Thus, the effect of GHG intensity reductions on this planetary boundary depends strongly on whether they are paired with ecologically restorative or ecologically harmful practices (Nissar et al., 2023), (Costa-Pierce et al., 2022).

Indicator 12 has an indirect positive impact on SDGs 3,6,8,12, and 13. Figure 12 illustrates the positive impacts of a reduced GHG emission intensity by fishing and aquaculture on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs.

Figure 12: Impacts of indicator 12 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 13: GHG emission intensities by food, beverage, and tobacco industries (NACE C10-C12)

In the EU, the food and beverage (F&B) industrial sector is the largest manufacturing sector in terms of value added, turnover, and employment. Although large companies only make up 1% of the food industry in the EU, they are responsible for almost half (48%) of the value added. The sector is associated with high levels of water consumption and wastewater production (Valta et al., 2015) and is a key contributor to anthropogenic GHG emissions. A study by Hansen et al. (2022) estimates that of the 50 largest F&B manufacturers in the world, 7 do not publicly or only incompletely report emissions and estimates that the emissions associated with these companies are 1.9-3.8 Gt of CO₂-eq. per year instead of the reported 0.9 Gt, meaning that between 53 and 77% of emissions go underreported. Direct emissions (scope 1) represent 8% of reported emissions, while indirect emissions of purchased energy (scope 2) and of the value chain (scope 3) account for 4% and 88%, respectively. The tobacco industry, on the other hand, is responsible for 84 Mt CO₂-eq. and 22,200 Mt water depletion, while 5.3 million hectares of land are used to grow tobacco (WHO, 2017). The food, beverage, and tobacco industries are therefore, apart from climate change, especially relevant for the planetary boundaries related to water and land use.

However, reducing GHG emission intensities does not automatically relieve pressure on these boundaries, as the outcomes depend strongly on the mitigation strategies employed. In practice, direct emissions from production (scope 1) and purchased energy (scope 2) constitute only a small fraction of total sector emissions, while most emissions are embedded in the value chain (scope 3), particularly in agriculture and livestock. Consequently, efforts to decarbonise the sector increasingly focus on upstream interventions, such as improving agricultural practices, promoting dietary shifts to reduce high-impact products, and increasing energy efficiency in processing. Circular approaches, like capturing and valorising organic waste, using low-carbon packaging, and integrating renewable utilities, also contribute to carbon reduction. Innovations such as green logistics, sustainable sourcing, and process optimisation are critical to ensuring that GHG reductions are accompanied by reduced water and land pressures.

Indicator 13 has an indirect positive impact on SDGs 3,6,8,12,13, and 15. Figure 13 illustrates the positive impacts of a reduced GHG emission intensity by the F&B and tobacco industries on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs.

Figure 13: Impacts of indicator 13 on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 14: GHG emission intensities from textiles (NACE C13-C15)

If the GHG emission intensity reductions in the textile industry are achieved through a decrease in production volumes, this will have a great positive impact on the Freshwater Change, the Novel Entities, and the Biosphere Integrity planetary boundaries. The EU Strategy for sustainable and circular textiles explicitly foresees a reduction in production through the “fast fashion is out of fashion” objective, as well as sets sustainability criteria for textiles in the EU including durability, repairability, and recyclability. By linking GHG-intensity reduction with production volume reduction and circular design, the textile sector can generate multiple environmental benefits on the three planetary boundaries apart from the three main ones that all GHG emission intensity indicators positively contribute to.

Direct positive impacts:

- Freshwater Change:** The textile industry is globally among the most water-intensive sectors. The dyeing and finishing stages alone are estimated to consume up to 93 billion m³ of freshwater annually and are accountable for around 20% of industrial water pollution (Bailey et al., 2022). While reducing GHG emissions through improved energy efficiency or process optimisation can curb fossil fuel use and CO₂ output, it does not by itself reduce the volume of water withdrawn or the pollution load generated. Only when GHG-intensity reductions are accompanied by shifts such as fewer garments produced, closed-loop wet processing, low-water dyeing technologies, or reuse and recycling can the pressure on freshwater resources be relieved.

- Biosphere Integrity:** The textile supply chain exerts significant pressure on biodiversity. Land-use change for fibre production, chemical pollution in processing, and microfibre release during wear and washing all negatively impact the biosphere integrity planetary boundary. For instance, approximately 700,000 microplastic fibres may be released during a single load of polyester clothing in the washing machine (EuroParl, 2020). Reducing GHG-intensity not just through energy optimisation but also through a decreased volume of production and use of chemicals and hazardous substances supports both genetic and functional biodiversity by reducing habitat conversion, chemical stress, and material throughput.
- Novel Entities:** The release of novel chemical entities, such as dyes, finishing agents, and microfibres, is a distinctive pressure from the textile industry. The sector is responsible for a substantial share of industrial wastewater contamination and microplastic discharge. For instance, fast-fashion textile dyeing is responsible for more than 20% of global clean water pollution. Emission-intensity reductions linked to design for circularity, reduced fabric volumes, recycled feedstocks, and chemical-free finishing, curtail the creation and dispersal of novel entities.

Indicator 14 has an indirect positive impact on SDGs 6,8,12,13, and 15. Figure 14 illustrates the positive impacts of a reduced GHG emission intensity from textiles on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs.

Figure 14: Impacts of indicator 14 on the planetary boundaries and the SDG
 Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 15: GHG emission intensity from wood products, except furniture (NACE C16)

A decrease in GHG emission intensity in the wood manufacturing sector (NACE C16) indicates progress towards greater climate efficiency and contributes directly to the EU’s climate-neutrality objectives under the European Green Deal, the Fit-for-55 package, and the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. Lower emission intensity could reflect improvements in energy efficiency, fuel substitution, and process innovation, supporting the broader transition to sustainable industrial decarbonisation. Moreover, wood products play a dual role in climate mitigation: they act as long-term carbon stores during their service life and substitute fossil-intensive materials such as steel or concrete, thereby further reducing overall greenhouse gas emissions across value chains.

Indirect positive impacts:

- **Land-system Change & Biosphere Integrity:** Efficient use of residues and recycled wood helps relieve pressure on forests, whereas increased primary extraction without sustainable management could intensify land-use change and biodiversity loss.

Indicator 15 has an indirect positive impact on SDGs 6,8,12,13, and 15. Figure 15 illustrates the positive impacts of a reduced GHG emission intensity from textiles on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs.

Figure 15: Impacts of indicator 15 on the planetary boundaries and the SDG
 Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 16: GHG emission intensity from paper and paper products (NACE C17)

Indirect mixed impacts:

- **Novel Entities:** Transitioning to lower-emission chemistries and closed-loop systems may reduce solvent/bleach effluents and VOCs, though trade-offs can arise if alternatives demand higher energy or introduce other additives.
- **Atmospheric Aerosol Loading:** Switching from fossil fuels to biomass residues in boilers can cut net GHGs but increase particulates without advanced controls; electrification of heat mitigates this risk.

Indicator 16 has an indirect positive impact on SDGs 6,8,12,13, and 15. Figure 16 illustrates the positive impacts of a reduced GHG emission intensity from textiles on the planetary boundaries and the SDGs.

Figure 16: Impacts of indicator 16 on the planetary boundaries and the SDG
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 17: Net GHG emissions from land use, land use change, and forestry (LULUCF) (index)

The indicator tracks net greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions/removals from the LULUCF sector such as the balance between emissions (e.g., from deforestation, drained organic soils) and removals in managed lands and forests. It expresses this balance as an index relative to a reference period to show trend changes over time. In the EU, LULUCF reporting follows UNFCCC/IPCC inventory guidance and is integrated into the EU policy framework under the LULUCF Regulation, which sets a binding EU-level net sink target of -310 Mt CO₂-eq. by 2030 (relative to the 2016-2018 average).

This indicator is formalised as follows:

Equation 8. Index of Net GHG emissions from land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF)

$$Index_t = \frac{E_{LULUCF,t}^{net}}{E_{LULUCF,base}^{net}} \times 100$$

The indicator shows how the land and forests sector (LULUCF) is doing for the climate over time. It turns the sector's net emissions or removals into a simple index compared with a chosen starting period (for example, 1990 or the 2016-2018 average). The index should make clear whether "higher" means a stronger sink or not.

In practice, a lower net number (more removals), or a higher index if defined as sink strength, means the land and forests are taking up more CO₂. Values moving toward zero or positive mean the sink is weakening or the sector becomes a source. This indicator is policy-relevant because it tracks progress towards climate goals (e.g., strengthening the land carbon sink by 2030) and helps target actions such as sustainable forest management, restoration, and peatland rewetting. Showing the index together with the actual net total (Mt CO₂-eq.) keeps the message easy to read.

Direct positive impacts:

- **Climate Change:** Strengthening the LULUCF sink directly lowers atmospheric CO₂; the index reflects whether removals are increasing (more negative flux) or weakening. It is important to highlight that removals are reversible (non-permanent) due to fires, pests, drought, and management choices.
- **Land-system change & Biosphere integrity:** Afforestation, restoration, and sustainable forest management can enhance sinks and biodiversity; poorly designed land conversions or intensive harvests can weaken sinks and harm ecosystems.

Indirect positive or mixed impact:

- **Freshwater change & Novel entities:** Peatland rewetting reduces CO₂ and N₂O but may have local water-quality trade-offs if not well managed; reduced agro-chemical inputs and better residue handling can support co-benefits. (Context-dependent; not captured by the index alone.)

This indicator is directly linked to SDG 13 and indirectly to SDG 12. Figure 17 shows which planetary boundaries and SDGs are positively affected by a reduced net GHG emissions from LULUCF.

Figure 17: Impacts of indicator 17 on the planetary boundaries and the SDG
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 18: Biomass footprint intensity - Raw material consumption (RMC)

The indicator measures the biomass material footprint per unit of economic output. It captures the raw materials (biomass) extracted worldwide to satisfy a country’s final demand (households, government, investment), allocated on a consumption basis and expressed as an intensity (e.g., tonnes per million-euro GDP). In Eurostat statistics, the material footprint is also called Raw Material Consumption (RMC) and is compiled using raw material equivalents (RME) of trade to account for global supply chains.

Formula:

Equation 9. Biomass footprint intensity

$$\text{Biomass footprint intensity} \left[\frac{\text{tonnes}}{\text{million EUR}} \right] = \frac{\text{biomass RMC (tonnes)}}{\text{GDP (e.g., chain linked, EUR)}}$$

The indicator shows how efficiently the economy uses biomass by relating the biomass raw material consumption (RMC) to economic output. It turns the biomass used worldwide to satisfy domestic demand into a simple intensity (e.g., tonnes per million euro of GDP) or an index against a chosen base year. The presentation should make clear whether a higher value means more biomass per euro (lower efficiency) or, if inverted, the opposite.

In practice, a lower intensity (or a higher index if defined as efficiency) means the economy generates the same value with less biomass, pointing to better resource efficiency, circular use

(reuse/recycling/cascading), and more sustainable sourcing. Rising values indicate greater pressure on biomass supply chains and land use. This indicator is policy-relevant because it supports circular economy and resource-efficiency goals, and helps target actions such as eco-design, recycling of bio-based flows, and verified sustainable sourcing. Showing the intensity alongside the actual biomass RMC (in tonnes) keeps the message easy to read.

Direct impact:

- **Land-system change:** Lower biomass footprint intensity directly reduces pressure for land conversion and harvest intensity by lowering the biomass extracted per unit of economic output; conversely, rising intensity raises land-use pressures.

Indirect positive or mixed impacts:

- **Biosphere integrity & Freshwater change:** Improved efficiency and circularity can ease **habitat disturbance** and **water demand** tied to biomass production; effects are context-dependent (crop/forest types, regions, practices).
- **Biogeochemical flows:** Lower demand for primary biomass can reduce fertiliser-driven nutrient loads along supply chains; however, substitution patterns matter.
- **Climate change:** While the indicator is not an emissions metric, reducing primary biomass extraction and transport can indirectly lower life cycle GHGs depending on energy mixes and logistics.

The biomass footprint intensity indicator is indirectly linked to SDG 12. Figure 18 shows which planetary boundaries and SDGs are positively affected by an efficient use of biomass.

Figure 18: Impacts of indicator 18 on the planetary boundaries and the SDG
Source: Own elaboration

Indicator 19: Water Exploitation Index (WEI)

The WEI quantifies the total annual freshwater withdrawal relative to the long-term average available renewable freshwater resources in a given territory and period. The indicator measures the volume of water abstracted and subsequently returned to the environment by different economic sectors, either before or after use. The difference between total abstractions and returns represents net water consumption. Although no formal targets have been established at the European level, values exceeding 20% are generally interpreted as indicative of water scarcity, while those equal to or above 40% signify severe water scarcity, pointing to an unsustainable use of freshwater. Annual national-level calculations of the WEI may, however, obscure local or seasonal variations in water availability, potentially concealing periods or regions experiencing significant water stress. The indicator is compiled by the European Environment Agency (EEA) using modelled data from the WISE SoE-Water Quantity database (WISE 3), supplemented by open data sources such as Eurostat and the OECD, and completed through gap-filling techniques.

The indicator is measured in % and is calculated as:

Equation 10. Water Exploitation Index (WEI)

$$WEI = \frac{\text{annual total freshwater abstraction}}{\text{long-term annual average available water from renewable freshwater resources}}$$

A low WEI (<20%) can indicate a direct positive impact on a third of the planetary boundaries, namely freshwater change, biosphere integrity, and biogeochemical flows (Bunsen et al., 2021).

Direct positive impact:

- **Freshwater Change:** Excessive water withdrawal (high WEI) reduces the environmental flow needed to sustain aquatic ecosystems, leading to the rapid loss of freshwater biodiversity. A low WEI is an indicator that we are operating within the safe zone of the Freshwater Change boundary. It indicates that human-induced disturbance of blue water flow (rivers, lakes, and groundwater) is minimal. This ensures that water resources are able to regenerate, avoiding the severe and unsustainable utilisation that occurs when the index reaches or exceeds 40 per cent.
- **Biosphere Integrity:** Excessive water withdrawal (high WEI) reduces the volume of water required to sustain natural and aquatic ecosystems, resulting in the rapid loss of freshwater biodiversity. Conversely, a low WEI ensures that sufficient water remains in rivers, lakes, and wetlands to maintain ecological integrity and support aquatic life. This is particularly important as freshwater biodiversity is declining faster than terrestrial biodiversity, largely due to overexploitation of water resources.
- **Biogeochemical Flows:** When water flow rates are reduced due to high withdrawal, pollutants and excess nutrients are concentrated. A low WEI, by ensuring stable or higher natural river flows, provides greater natural dilution and dispersion capacity. This mitigates the concentration of nutrient runoff from agricultural and industrial activities, thereby reducing the risk of nutrient overloading and widespread harmful algal blooms (eutrophication) in freshwater bodies (EPA, n.d.).

The WEI is directly linked to SDG 6 and indirectly to 7 and 13. Figure 19 shows which planetary boundaries and SDGs are positively affected by a low WEI.

Figure 19: Impacts of indicator 19 on the planetary boundaries and the SDG
Source: Own elaboration

3.2.3. Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs

The bioeconomy represents a significant component of the EU's economy. In 2018, employment within the EU bioeconomy reached 18.4 million people, although this figure has been declining, primarily due to reductions in the agricultural workforce resulting from sector consolidation and increased efficiency achieved through optimisation, automation, and digitalisation (Prause, 2021). Data for the EU-28 indicate that turnover in the bioeconomy has steadily risen, from under EUR 2 trillion in 2008 to over EUR 2.43 trillion in 2018, with the food sector accounting for the largest share. Given the emphasis placed on the bioeconomy's potential in EU policy frameworks, including the EU Bioeconomy Strategy and the Green Deal, it is increasingly important to monitor the sector economically.

In SUSTRACK, we focus on two indicators for the category “bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs”. These are:

- Bioeconomy gross value added (GVA) per person
- Share of employment in bio-based sectors

Indicator 20: Bioeconomy Gross Value Added (GVA) per person

This indicator is fundamentally a measure of labour productivity, defined as the total GVA generated by bio-based sectors divided by the number of persons employed in the bioeconomy.

Analysis of the indicator reveals significant structural and regional differences across EU Member States. Between 2012 and 2021, real value added in the EU bioeconomy sectors increased by 39 %, largely driven by growth in bio-based manufacturing. Despite this expansion, employment declined by 1.3 million jobs over the same period, primarily reflecting reductions in the agricultural workforce. The structure of the EU bioeconomy varies considerably across Member States: Eastern and Southern European countries generally exhibit higher shares of bio-based sectors in terms of both GDP and total employment, reflecting their specialisation in primary production. These regions also experienced the greatest declines in agricultural employment, which contributed to improvements in labour productivity.

While turnover data are often cited to illustrate the economic significance of the bioeconomy, such as the dominance of the food, beverage, and tobacco sector in EU bioeconomy turnover (51 %) compared with its value-added share (38 %), value added is increasingly considered the more meaningful indicator, as it avoids double counting and reflects the actual economic contribution of a sector. Agriculture, for example, contributes relatively more to value added than to turnover (28 % versus 17 %). EU- and Member State-level analyses by the JRC, the nova-Institute, and studies such as MontBioeco demonstrate these structural differences, highlighting the importance of monitoring value added alongside employment and turnover to understand both the economic performance and sustainability implications of the bioeconomy (GIUNTOLI et al., 2020), (Porc et al., 2020), (Lier et al.). Despite certain limitations of value added and GDP as indicators in the context of sustainable development, they remain key measures for comparing bioeconomic growth to the broader economy and for informing policy aimed at fostering a sustainable and circular bio-based economy (Ronzon & M'Barek, 2018).

Crucially, it's important to note that productivity growth cannot rely on traditional methods of resource intensification, as this risks exacerbating the transgression of planetary boundaries. For this indicator to be considered sustainable and align with planetary boundaries, the growth in GVA per person must be fundamentally decoupled from resource depletion and instead be driven by increasing the value derived from existing biomass, wastes, and residues, and an innovative and cascading use of resources. At the same time, increases in labour productivity should not come at the expense of employment losses or social equity, as this would undermine the social foundations of sustainable development (e.g. SDG 8 on Decent Work and Economic Growth). Lakner et al. (2021) find that novel bio-based industries tend to have a high GVA and less labour intensity, thereby generating a higher value added per employee. This highlights the need for balanced strategies that combine technological innovation and efficiency improvements with just transition measures to safeguard employment opportunities in the evolving bioeconomy.

While GVA indicators measure the value generated, they don't by themselves indicate whether growth is decoupled from resource use. To address this, the bioeconomy GVA indicator can be interpreted in conjunction with metrics of bioeconomy-specific resource productivity, such as the ratio of bioeconomy GVA to the biomass material footprint per capita. This approach allows for an assessment of whether increases in economic value are achieved through more efficient and innovative use of resources, rather than through increased extraction or unsustainable consumption. Moreover, sustainable growth would be indicated by the annual growth rate of the bioeconomy GVA per person exceeding the per-capita reduction rate of bio-based material use, signalling that economic activity in bio-based sectors is being expanded while simultaneously reducing the volume of bio-based materials used, and therefore the pressure on planetary

boundaries such as biosphere integrity, land-system change, and climate change. By linking GVA to material efficiency, this approach provides a more comprehensive perspective on the sustainability of bioeconomic development, highlighting the importance of concurrently monitoring all of the 21 Sustrack indicators and establishing interconnections, capturing trade-offs and synergies, and ultimately developing a holistic understanding of progress towards a sustainable and circular bioeconomy.

This indicator has an indirect positive impact on SDGs 8 and 9.

Indicator 21: Share of Employment in Bio-based Sectors

This metric tracks job creation and its contribution to inclusive growth by measuring the total number of persons employed in bio-based sectors as a proportion of total employment. However, applying sustainability thresholds to this indicator is not straightforward, as there are no policy-defined criteria or targets that determine when employment in the bioeconomy is considered sustainable. In this context, performance thresholds would need to be interpreted more qualitatively, for instance in relation to maintaining or improving overall employment levels, ensuring fair labour conditions, and avoiding social exclusion.

This indicator must be carefully analysed alongside GVA per person. If employment growth primarily occurs in low-productivity primary sectors, it may lead to unsustainable demands for land and raw biomass, counteracting decoupling efforts. Conversely, excessive productivity-driven labour reductions without corresponding job creation in higher value-added sectors may breach social sustainability thresholds related to employment security and equality.

Employment within the European bioeconomy is unevenly distributed across sectors. While agriculture and forestry together account for less than one quarter of total bioeconomy turnover, they employ more than half of the workforce, reflecting the labour-intensive nature of primary biomass production. When combined with the food and feed industries, these sectors represent over three-quarters of total bioeconomy employment within the EU. In contrast, the bio-based industries, such as bio-based chemicals, materials, and bioenergy, collectively employ just over three million people across Member States. Although overall employment in the bioeconomy has shown a gradual decline over recent years, largely due to structural changes and efficiency gains in primary sectors, employment within bio-based industries has remained comparatively stable. Turnover trends reveal the opposite dynamic: while the total bioeconomy turnover has remained relatively constant, the bio-based industries have exhibited more year-to-year variability, with a slight decrease recorded in 2021. This divergence underscores the structural evolution of the bioeconomy, suggesting a gradual shift from traditional primary production towards more value-added bio-based industrial activities (Porc et al., 2020).

Despite the central objective of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy to strengthen European competitiveness and create sustainable jobs, long-term projections indicate a continued contraction in bioeconomy employment. Results from the [BioMonitor Project](#) find that total EU bioeconomy employment is projected to fall from 21.5 million persons in 2020 to 18.4 million by 2050. The sharpest reductions are expected in primary agriculture, where employment is set to drop from 7.1 million to 4.9 million over the same period, driven by labour-saving productivity gains and stable food demand. Employment in bio-based industries, estimated at 3.1 million in 2020, is expected to decline only slightly to 2.8 million by 2050, reflecting comparatively greater resilience in these higher value-added sectors. Additionally, ambitious bio-industrial expansion and sustainability measures (such as halving household food waste) are projected to further reduce total employment in the EU's bioeconomy. This highlights the importance of developing complementary indicators, such as overall employment rates, gender equality, income

distribution, and social inclusion metrics, that can better capture the social dimension of sustainability. To mitigate potential job displacement, particularly in rural areas where agricultural employment remains a key livelihood, policy measures must prioritise retraining, upskilling, and reskilling initiatives for workers transitioning out of declining sectors. Monitoring the share of employment in bio-based sectors, especially on a regional level, is therefore very important.

This indicator also has an indirect positive impact on SDGs 8 and 9.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This report set out to identify sustainability thresholds for the 21 indicators defined in SUSTRACK as relevant to an EU circular bioeconomy. The analysis revealed a conceptual and practical gap between scientifically derived sustainability thresholds, such as those defined under the planetary boundaries framework, and the policy- and statistically based indicators typically employed in bioeconomy monitoring and decision-making frameworks.

However, formulating fixed, scientifically robust thresholds for many of these indicators is neither scientifically meaningful nor conducive to informed decision-making, as absolute values tend to obscure systemic interdependencies, regional variations, and evolving pressures on and transgressions of the planetary boundaries. Moreover, the development of science-based thresholds lies beyond current scientific feasibility, given the complexity and inherently long-term nature of such work. The scientific literature provides a robust conceptual foundation for sustainability thresholds, yet these are generally defined at global or biophysical levels, often linked to control variables (e.g. atmospheric CO₂ concentration, nitrogen flows, freshwater use) that do not directly correspond to the policy indicators most commonly used in statistical databases (e.g. recycling rate, resource productivity, GHG emission intensity). As a result, translating absolute sustainability concepts into operational, country-level monitoring systems such as the SUSTRACK framework remains a methodological challenge.

Consequently, this report focuses on performance thresholds, drawing on policy-based thresholds and targets where available, as practical and credible entry points for sustainability monitoring, while laying the foundation for future dynamic, science-informed thresholds that can adapt to shifting planetary conditions and socio-economic developments.

In this regard, the emerging field of Absolute Environmental Sustainability Assessment (AESA), which integrates the PBs framework into Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), offers a promising methodological pathway. Recent work, such as Paulillo et al. (2026) illustrates both the potential and complexity of this approach, showing that current EU consumption patterns remain environmentally unsustainable under most allocation and harmonisation principles, and that methodological choices can substantially influence outcomes. This highlights the need for further methodological convergence, transparency, and sensitivity analysis when operationalising planetary-boundary-based thresholds.

From our analysis, we conclude that rather than relying on static values, future threshold frameworks should increasingly adopt dynamic, rate-based expressions that capture whether economic development is being decoupled from environmental pressures, such as when GDP growth outpaces reductions in domestic material consumption (see indicator 7, resource productivity). This shift would enable thresholds to evolve alongside scientific insights, reflect interactions between the SDGs and planetary boundaries, and support a holistic assessment across all 21 indicators by acknowledging their interdependencies and cumulative impacts.

The planetary boundaries framework provided a critical lens for the analysis in this report. Current scientific assessments indicate that seven of the nine boundaries have already been transgressed, with only stratospheric ozone depletion and atmospheric aerosol loading remaining within the safe operating space. These two are also the least affected by the 21 indicators examined here. In contrast, climate change and ocean acidification are influenced by nearly all indicators, while freshwater change, land-system change, and biogeochemical flows are impacted by the vast majority. This highlights the importance of setting ambitious targets for the indicators and closely monitoring them, as they directly affect the boundaries under the greatest pressure. Prioritising these areas enables policymakers to target interventions where they are most urgently needed and to steer the transition toward a sustainable, circular bioeconomy that supports a return to a safe operating space for humanity.

Looking ahead, bridging the gap between planetary-boundary-based sustainability thresholds and policy-relevant performance indicators will be essential. This may involve the development of downscaled or sector-specific boundary allocations, integration of dynamic rate-based metrics, and closer harmonisation of environmental assessment frameworks with statistical monitoring systems. Such efforts will strengthen the capacity of circular bioeconomy monitoring not only to track policy progress but also to remain anchored in the biophysical realities that define long-term sustainability.

REFERENCES

- Bailey, K., Basu, A., & Sharma, S. (2022). The Environmental Impacts of Fast Fashion on Water Quality: A Systematic Review. *Water*, 14(7).
- Bouwman, L., Goldewijk, K. K., Van Der Hoek, K. W., Beusen, A. H. W., Van Vuuren, D. P., Willems, J., Rufino, M. C., & Stehfest, E. (2013). Exploring global changes in nitrogen and phosphorus cycles in agriculture induced by livestock production over the 1900-2050 period. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 110(52), 20882-20887. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1073/pnas.1012878108>
- Bunson, J., Berger, M., & Finkbeiner, M. (2021). Planetary boundaries for water - A review. *Ecological Indicators*, 121, 107022. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.107022>
- Campbell, B. M., Beare, D. J., Bennett, E. M., Hall-Spencer, J. M., Ingram, J. S., Jaramillo, F., Ortiz, R., Ramankutty, N., Sayer, J. A., & Shindell, D. (2017). Agriculture production as a major driver of the Earth system exceeding planetary boundaries. *Ecology and society*, 22(4).
- Costa-Pierce, B. A., Bockus, A. B., Buck, B. H., van den Burg, S. W. K., Chopin, T., Ferreira, J. G., Goseberg, N., Heasman, K. G., Johansen, J., Shumway, S. E., Sims, N. A., & Tacon, A. G. J. (2022). A Fishy Story Promoting a False Dichotomy to Policy-Makers: It Is Not Freshwater vs. Marine Aquaculture. *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture*, 30(4), 429-446. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2021.2014175>
- Drosg, B., Fuchs, W., Al Seadi, T., Madsen, M., & Linke, B. (2015). *Nutrient recovery by biogas digestate processing* (Vol. 2015). IEA Bioenergy Dublin.
- EC. (2009). COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE COUNCIL AND THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT: GDP and beyond Measuring progress in a changing world.
- EC. (2025). Transforming food systems to return to Earth's limits. Available at: https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/publication/transforming-food-systems-return-earths-limits_en.
- EC. (n.d.). International Conference on Forests for Biodiversity and Climate. Available at: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/nature-and-biodiversity/international-conference-forests-biodiversity-and-climate_en.
- EEA. (2022). Reaching 2030's residual municipal waste target – why recycling is not enough. Available at: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/reaching-2030s-residual-municipal-waste-target-why-recycling-is-not-enough#:~:text=Reaching%202030's%20residual%20municipal%20waste%20target%20%E2%80%94%20why%20recycling%20is%20not%20enough,-Briefing%20Published%2025&text=Municipal%20waste%20accounts%20for%2027,be%20key%20to%20reaching%20them>.
- EPA. (2025). Human Health & Environmental Impacts of the Electric Power Sector. Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/power-sector/human-health-environmental-impacts-electric-power-sector>.

- EPA. (n.d.). Basic Information on Nutrient Pollution. Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/nutrientpollution/basic-information-nutrient-pollution>.
- EuroParl. (2020). Fast fashion: EU laws for sustainable textile consumption. Available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20201208STO93327/fast-fashion-eu-laws-for-sustainable-textile-consumption?utm_source=chatgpt.com.
- Eurostat. (2025a). Municipal waste statistics. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Municipal_waste_statistics.
- Eurostat. (2025b). Resource productivity statistics. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Resource_productivity_statistics#:~:text=Highlights,03%20%202025.xlsx%5D%5D.
- Eurostat. (n.d.). Glossary: Domestic material consumption (DMC). Available at: [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Domestic_material_consumption_\(DMC\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Domestic_material_consumption_(DMC)).
- Favoino, E., Giavini, M., & Rupp, M. (2020). Bio-waste generation in the EU: Current capture levels and future potential. *Bio-based Industries Consortium (IBC)*.
- Ferretto, A., Matthews, R., Brooker, R., & Smith, P. (2022). Planetary Boundaries and the Doughnut frameworks: A review of their local operability. *Anthropocene*, 39, 100347. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ancene.2022.100347>
- GIUNTOLI, J., ROBERT, N., RONZON, T., SANCHEZ, L. J., FOLLADOR, M., GIRARDI, I., BARREDO, C., BORZACCHIELLO, M. T., SALA, S., & M'BAREK, R. (2020). Building a monitoring system for the EU bioeconomy.
- Hammond, A., Adriaanse, A., Rodenburg, E., Bryant, D., & Woodward, R. (1995). ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATORS: A Systematic Approach to Measuring and Reporting on Environmental Policy Performance in the Context of Sustainable Development.
- Hansen, A. D., Kuramochi, T., & Wicke, B. (2022). The status of corporate greenhouse gas emissions reporting in the food sector: An evaluation of food and beverage manufacturers. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 361, 132279. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132279>
- Ingrao, C., Strippoli, R., Lagioia, G., & Huisingh, D. (2023). Water scarcity in agriculture: An overview of causes, impacts and approaches for reducing the risks. *Heliyon*, 9(8), e18507. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18507>
- Kern, M., Raussen, T., Graven, T., Bergs, C., & Hermann, T. (2012). Ecologically sustainable recovery of bio-waste. *Published by the German Federal Ministry of the Environment, nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU) and German Federal Environment Agency (UBA)* http://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/378/publikationen/ecologically_sustainable_recovery_of_bio-waste_bf.pdf, last accessed, 20, 2017.

- Ladu, L., & Morone, P. (2021). Holistic approach in the evaluation of the sustainability of bio-based products: An Integrated Assessment Tool. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 28, 911-924e916. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.07.006>
- Lakner, Z., Oláh, J., Popp, J., & Balázs, E. (2021). The structural change of the economy in the context of the bioeconomy. *EFB Bioeconomy Journal*, 1, 100018. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioeco.2021.100018>
- Lier, M., Aarne, M., Korhonen, K. T., Kärkkäinen, L., Yli-Viikari, A., & Packalen, T. MontBioeco-Synthesis on bioeconomy monitoring systems in the EU Member States.
- Malatyinszki, S., Zéman, Z., & Kálmán, B. G. (2025). Resource productivity and sustainability—a comparison of two European countries. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 12(1), 238. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-025-04428-4>
- Nissar, S., Bakhtiyar, Y., Arafat, M. Y., Andrabi, S., Mir, Z. A., Khan, N. A., & Langer, S. (2023). The evolution of integrated multi-trophic aquaculture in context of its design and components paving way to valorization via optimization and diversification. *Aquaculture*, 565, 739074. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2022.739074>
- Oberle, B., Bringezu, S., Hatfield-Dodds, S., Hellweg, S., Schandl, H., & Clement, J. (2019). *Global Resources Outlook: 2019* (978-92-807-3741-7). <https://www.resourcepanel.org/reports/global-resources-outlook>
- Paulillo, A., Wierzgala, P., Biganzoli, F., & Sanyé-Mengual, E. (2026). Investigating methodological aspects of absolute environmental sustainability assessment based on planetary boundaries. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 117, 108154. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2025.108154>
- Porc, O., Hark, N., Carus, M., Dammer, L., BIC, D. C., & Knapsack, C. (2020). European bioeconomy in figures. In.
- Prause, L. (2021). Digital Agriculture and Labor: A Few Challenges for Social Sustainability. *Sustainability*, 13(11).
- Ronzon, T., & M'Barek, R. (2018). Socioeconomic Indicators to Monitor the EU's Bioeconomy in Transition. *Sustainability*, 10(6), 1745.
- Srebotnjak, T., Polzin, C., Giljum, S., Herbert, S., & Lutter, S. (2010). Establishing environmental sustainability thresholds and indicators. *Final report. Ecologic Institute and SERI*.
- Tomalka, J., Hunecke, C., Murken, L., Heckmann, T., Cronauer, C., Becker, R., Collignon, Q., Collins-Sowah, P., Crawford, M., & Gloy, N. (2024). Stepping back from the precipice: Transforming land management to stay within planetary boundaries. Potsdam, Germany: Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48485/pik.2024.018>. The views expressed in this report are those of the authors. *Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Telegrafenberg A*, 31, 14473.
- Tonini, D., Garcia-Gutierrez, P., & Nessi, S. (2021). Environmental effects of plastic waste recycling. *European Commission*.
- UN. (2025). Goal 12: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns. Available at: https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal12#progress_and_info.

- UNEP. (2021). Our global food system is the primary driver of biodiversity loss. Available at: <https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/press-release/our-global-food-system-primary-driver-biodiversity-loss>.
- UNESCO. (2024). Water for Prosperity and Peace: Statistics. Available at: <https://www.unesco.org/reports/wwdr/en/2024/s>.
- Valta, K., Kosanovic, T., Malamis, D., Moustakas, K., & Loizidou, M. (2015). Overview of water usage and wastewater management in the food and beverage industry. *Desalination and Water Treatment*, 53(12), 3335-3347. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2014.934100>
- Verburg, P. H., Mertz, O., Erb, K.-H., Haberl, H., & Wu, W. (2013). Land system change and food security: towards multi-scale land system solutions. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 5(5), 494-502. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2013.07.003>
- WHO. (2017). Tobacco and its environmental impact: an overview.

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